

NASA's Earth Science Flight Program Meets the Challenges of Today and Tomorrow

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Abstract— The National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) Earth science flight program is a dynamic undertaking that consists of a large fleet of operating satellites, an array of satellite and instrument projects in various stages of development, a robust airborne science program, and a massive data archiving and distribution system. Each element of the flight program is complex and presents unique challenges. NASA builds upon its successes and learns from its setbacks to manage this evolving portfolio to meet NASA's Earth science objectives. NASA fleet of 19 operating missions provides a wide range of scientific measurements obtained from dedicated Earth science satellites and from instruments mounted to the International Space Station (ISS). Projects in development are divided into two broad categories: systematic missions and pathfinders. The Earth Systematic Missions (ESM) program includes a range of multi-disciplinary Earth-observing research satellite missions aimed at understanding the Earth system and its response to natural and human-induced forces and changes. The Earth System Science Pathfinder (ESSP) program provides frequent, regular, competitively selected Earth science research opportunities that accommodate new and emerging scientific priorities and measurement capabilities. The Earth Science Airborne Science Program provides manned and unmanned aircraft systems that further science and advance the use of satellite data. NASA uses these assets worldwide in campaigns to investigate extreme weather events, observe Earth system processes, obtain data for Earth science modeling activities, test and refine new instrument technologies, and calibrate instruments flying aboard Earth science spacecraft. Through the Earth Observing System Data and Information System (EOSDIS) NASA's Earth Science Division acquires, preserves, and distributes observational data from operating spacecraft to support Earth Science research focus areas. In addition, the Earth science flight program benefits from investments by the Earth Science Technology Office (ESTO) to develop and demonstrate cutting-edge technologies that can be reliably applied to the diverse needs of future NASA Earth science measurements and mission. NASA's current Earth Science portfolio is responsive to national scientific priorities. As the program evolves into the future, it will leverage the lessons learned from the current missions in operations and development, and plan for adjustments to future objectives in response to the needs of the United States and the Earth science community.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In 2007, the National Research Council wrote that “Understanding the complex, changing planet on which we live, how it supports life and how human activities affect its ability to do so in the future is one of the greatest intellectual challenges facing humanity. It is also one of the most important challenges for society as it seeks to achieve prosperity, health, and sustainability.” [1] One of NASA's strategic goals is to “Advance understanding of Earth and develop technologies to improve the quality of life on our home planet.” [2] Key to achieving this goal is to address four fundamental questions about the Earth: “How is the global Earth system changing? What causes these changes in the Earth system? How will the Earth system change in the future? How can Earth system science provide societal benefit?” [3] NASA's Earth Science Division breaks these four questions down as: characterize, understand, predict, and apply. The Earth science flight program is focused on the “characterize” piece of this puzzle.

The Earth science flight program is complex and varied, comprising of a large fleet of operating missions, multiple satellites and instruments in formulation and development, an airborne science program to complement the spaceborne assets, and an extensive data archiving and distribution

system. In addition, the flight program interfaces with other elements of the Earth Science Division (research, applied science, and technology) to address the challenges of NASA’s Earth science strategic goal. Each aspect of the flight program is dynamic and presents unique challenges. NASA builds upon its successes and learns from its setbacks to manage this evolving portfolio to meet NASA’s Earth science objectives.

The National Research Council’s 2007 *Earth Science and Applications from Space: National Imperatives for the Next Decade and Beyond*, commonly referred to as the Earth Science Decadal Survey, guides the current framework of the program, along with the 2010 *Responding to the Challenge of Climate and Environmental Change: NASA’s Plan for a Climate-Centric Architecture for Earth Observations and Applications from Space* [4]. These documents identify specific mission priorities for NASA, that are currently being implemented or are under planning.

2. OPERATING MISSIONS

The NASA Earth science fleet currently consists of 19 missions, covering all six of the Earth science focus areas (Atmospheric Composition, Carbon Cycle & Ecosystems, Climate Variability & Change, Earth Surface & Interior, Water & Energy Cycle, and Weather). Figure 1 shows the current set of operating missions, including their launch dates. Dates in green indicate that a mission is in primary operations, while orange indicates it is in extended operations.

Most of the missions are designed for systematic measurements of essential earth system parameters. Others are motivated by discovery and science community-driven priorities. Although all missions were conceived as research missions, it has turned out that the efficiency of the communications and ground data handling systems has supported operational and near-real-time applications. NASA’s interagency partners have rated most NASA missions as “High Utility” for operational applications, with Terra, Aqua, Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission (TRMM) and Suomi National Polar-orbiting Partnership (Suomi-NPP) rated “Very High”. Nearly all missions have met their original success criteria and are meeting the objective for sustained measurements on decadal time scales. This objective is met not only due to satellite longevity, but also to the sustained calibration/validation program. Also, data communications and ground data handling systems have supported operational and near-real-time applications.

Continued operation of the missions is determined through a biennial science review process, called the “Senior Review”, which evaluates the continuing science value. Operational uses of the missions are considered in the review, but science remains the defining factor for continuation. All 19 missions are currently producing data, but 11 are operating past their design lifetimes in extended missions. With several showing signs of aging and two planned for decommissioning in 2016, the Senior Review will need to make difficult decisions as to how to prioritize the missions for additional two-year extensions. Table 1 outlines the operating missions, their baseline mission life, current years of operation, and science focus.

Figure 1. Earth Science Operating Missions

Table 1. NASA Earth Science Operating Missions

Mission	Launch Date	Phase	Baseline Lifetime (yr)	Current Life (Yr)	Mission Website	Science Focus
Aqua	2002	Extended	6	13.5	aqua.nasa.gov	Water Variables
Aura	2004	Extended	6	11.3	aura.gsfc.nasa.gov	Atmospheric Chemistry
CALIPSO	2006	Extended	3	9.5	www-calipso.larc.nasa.gov	Clouds and Aerosols
CATS	2015	Prime	2	0.8	cats.gsfc.nasa.gov	Clouds and Aerosols
Cloudsat	2006	Extended	2	9.5	cloudsat.atmos.colorado.edu	Cloud Structure
DSCOVR	2015	Prime	2	0.7	www.nesdis.noaa.gov/DSCOVR/	Space Weather/Atmospheric Properties
EO-1	2000	Extended	1.5	14.9	eo1.gsfc.nasa.gov	Land Imaging
GPM	2014	Prime	3	1.7	pmm.nasa.gov/gpm	Global Precipitation
GRACE	2002	Extended	5	13.6	www.csr.utexas.edu/grace	Earth's Gravity Field
Landsat-7	1999	Extended	5	16.5	landsat.gsfc.nasa.gov/?p=3184	Land Imaging
Landsat-8	2013	Prime	5	2.7	landsat.gsfc.nasa.gov/?page_id=4071	Land Imaging
OCO-2	2014	Prime	2	1.3	oco.jpl.nasa.gov	Atmospheric Carbon Dioxide
OSTM/Jason-2	2008	Extended	3	7.3	sealevel.jpl.nasa.gov/missions/ostmjason2	Ocean Surface Topography
QuikSCAT	1999	Extended	3	16.4	winds.jpl.nasa.gov/missions/quikscat	Radar Cross-Sections and Near Surface Winds
RapidScat	2014	Prime	2	1.1	winds.jpl.nasa.gov/missions/RapidScat/	Ocean Vector Winds
SMAP	2015	Prime	3	0.7	smap.jpl.nasa.gov	Global Soil Moisture
SORCE	2003	Extended	5	12.8	lasp.colorado.edu/home/sorce/	Solar Irradiance
Suomi-NPP	2011	Prime	5	4.0	npp.gsfc.nasa.gov/suomi.html	Climate and Biological Productivity
Terra	1999	Extended	6	15.9	terra.nasa.gov	Earth System Components

The median age of the operating missions is over eight years, which presents challenges to both engineering and science teams. The engineering teams must respond to anomalies and determine operational workarounds as the observatory capabilities degrade; the science teams must maintain the dataset quality by determining the impact on the raw data and updating the retrieval algorithms. The most prevalent issue faced by the Earth science missions is currently battery degradation. At this time, four missions have reduced data collection, because the batteries cannot support the full load during eclipse, and one mission, Active Cavity Radiometer Irradiance Monitor Satellite (ACRIMSAT), was lost in 2014 due to battery failure. Battery management is an intensive daily operations task for Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment (GRACE), Solar Radiation and Climate Experiment (SORCE), QuikSCAT and CloudSat, requiring adjustments in the charging schemes and reducing battery loads during eclipse by turning off sensors and changing the operating mode. For example, both CloudSat and SORCE use a hibernation mode during orbit night by switching from 3-axis control to a spin-stabilized attitude, then reacquiring the sun upon orbit day. [5] At this time, GRACE is managing its batteries through offloading of sensors, rather than spacecraft subsystems, but the thermal effect on the data must be addressed through the algorithms. This is also the case for SORCE, where the data are also affected by thermal stability.

Another issue facing operational missions, is NASA must continually monitor their positions to avoid collisions with other satellites. Increased solar activity has led to more uncertainty in collision analysis calculations and consequently intensified analysis and planning activities to determine collision avoidance maneuvers. A history of collision avoidance maneuvers is shown in the Figure 2. Active monitoring of close approach events has steadily increased since 2008. In addition, potential conjunctions

between operational, maneuverable satellites have increased, necessitating communication between the satellite operators in order to coordinate avoidance maneuver planning. In addition to increasing the resources dedicated to collision assessment, NASA continually improves the agency's orbital debris procedures, and invests in analysis tool improvements.

Several of the NASA missions fly in constellations, which enhance the science return of the individual missions by forming a virtual platform and merging data from several satellites. The most complex of the constellations is the Afternoon Constellation, also known as the "A-Train." In this constellation, six satellites fly in close proximity to each other, enabling nearly simultaneous observations of the same and related phenomena using multiple observation techniques (see figure 3). Although each mission is independently controlled and operated, this type of convoy arrangement requires coordination among the operators to ensure satellite safety [6], as well as an open data policy that enables the different missions to share and merge the data at the lowest possible levels.

With the recent decommissioning of two missions and the expectation of another two decommissioning in 2016, the continuity of the datasets must be addressed if climate data records are to be maintained. Even when successor missions are already on-orbit or planned, the older dataset must be adequately documented and preserved for future research. All operating NASA missions are requested to plan adequately for post-mission reprocessing and expected to satisfy a data preservation specification developed by the Earth Science Data and Information System (ESDIS) project.

Figure 2. Collision Avoidance Maneuver History

Figure 3. Afternoon Constellation (A-Train) Observations [7]

3. MISSIONS IN DEVELOPMENT

Projects in development are divided into two broad categories: systematic missions and pathfinders. The ESM program includes a broad range of multi-disciplinary Earth-observing research satellite missions and instruments aimed at understanding the Earth system and its response to natural and human-induced forces and changes. Understanding these forces will help determine how to predict future changes, and how to mitigate or adapt to these changes. The ESSP program provides frequent, regular, competitively selected Earth science research opportunities that accommodate new and emerging scientific priorities and measurement capabilities. This results in a series of relatively low-cost, small-sized investigations and missions. Principal investigators (PIs), whose scientific objectives support a variety of studies, lead these missions, including studies of the atmosphere, oceans, land surface, polar ice regions, or solid Earth. This portfolio of missions and investigations provides opportunity for investment in innovative Earth science that enhances NASA's capability for better understanding the current state of the Earth system.

An important sub-element of the ESSP Program is Venture Class. This initiative was developed in direct response to a recommendation from the 2007 NRC Earth science Decadal Survey, which stated "to restore more frequent launch opportunities and to facilitate the demonstration of innovative ideas and higher-risk technologies, NASA should create a new Venture class of low-cost research and application missions." [1]. These Venture Class investigations are science-driven and PI-led. The projects are also cost- and schedule-constrained. Venture Class investigations complement the systematic missions identified in the Decadal Survey, and provide flexibility to accommodate scientific advances and new implementation approaches. Venture Class is a fully funded element of the flight program, with three "strands" (suborbital investigations, missions, and instruments) that are regularly solicited. Earth Venture Suborbital (EVS) investigations are solicited every five years. Complete small missions, identified as Earth Venture Missions (EVMs) are solicited every four years. Earth Venture Instruments (EVIs) are missions of opportunity solicited every 18 months.

The ESM and ESSP projects often involve partnerships with other U.S. agencies and/or international organizations. This adds to the complexity of mission development, but allows for a greater scientific return on NASA's investments.

As of October 1, 2015, NASA Earth science has nine projects that are either in the development process, or are about to begin development.

The Stratospheric Aerosol and Gas Experiment III (SAGE III) project is an ESM project planned for delivery and integration with the ISS in 2016. SAGE III will make atmospheric measurements of ozone, aerosols, and other trace gases using a ultraviolet/visible spectrometer

employing an occultation technique. In addition, limb scatter observations will be used in a research mode to improve spatial coverage. The European Space Agency (ESA) contributed the SAGE III pointing platform, via the ISS Program.

Also in 2016, NASA will launch the EVM Cyclone Global Navigation Satellite System (CYGNSS) mission. CYGNSS is a constellation of eight microsatellites that will collect measurements of ocean surface winds, using direct and refracted global positioning system (GPS) signals, to better understand the formation and intensification of tropical cyclones.

The Earth science flight program has two ESM projects planned for launch in 2017. The Gravity Recovery And Climate Experiment Follow-On (GRACE-FO) mission will measure variations in gravity over Earth's surface, using microwave ranging, accelerometer data, and GPS receivers, to extend the collection of data from the original GRACE project. GRACE FO is a collaborative mission with the German Research Centre for Geosciences (GFZ). The Ice, Cloud, and land Elevation Satellite-2 (ICESat-2) mission will utilize laser altimetry to measure ice sheet elevation changes, sea ice thickness, and provide data to estimate global vegetation biomass.

In 2018, NASA will deliver two EVIs to the ISS. The Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation (GEDI) instrument will use lidar measurements to characterize the effects of changing climate and land use on ecosystem structure and dynamics. The ECOsystem Spaceborne Thermal Radiometer Experiment on Space Station (ECOSTRESS) instrument will provide insight into plant-water dynamics and how ecosystems change with climate via thermal infrared radiometer measurements of evapotranspiration.

Also in 2018, another EVI will be delivered, called Tropospheric Emissions: Monitoring of Pollution (TEMPO). The TEMPO instrument is a hosted payload, meaning that it will fly on a yet-to-be-determined geostationary satellite. TEMPO will make spectroscopic measurements of Ozone, Nitrogen, and Formaldehyde over North America.

Further on the horizon, NASA has several ESM projects planned for launch in the early 2020s. The Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT) Mission is a broad swath radar altimetry mission being developed in partnership with the French space agency, Centre National d'Etudes Spatiales (CNES), supporting oceanographic and hydrologic objectives. NASA is also collaborating with the Indian Space Research Organisation (ISRO) on the NASA-ISRO Synthetic Aperture Radar (NISAR) mission. NISAR's science objectives are to understand the response of ice sheets to climate change and the interaction of sea ice and climate; understand the dynamics of carbon storage and uptake in wooded, agricultural, wetland, and permafrost systems; and determine the likelihood of earthquakes,

volcanic eruptions, and landslides. Landsat 9 is the latest in a series of Landsat satellites that have continuously acquired multispectral images of the global land surface since 1972. The Landsat 9 will extend the ability to detect and characterize changes on the global land surface. Landsat 9 is being developed in coordination with the United States Geological Survey (USGS). The Pre-Aerosol, Clouds, and ocean Ecosystem (PACE) project is being planned to make global ocean color measurements to provide extended data records on ocean ecology and global biogeochemistry, as well as polarimetry measurements to provide extended data records on clouds and aerosols. NASA is also in the early planning stages for other missions to enter development, including the Climate Absolute Radiance and Refractivity Observatory (CLARREO), Orbiting Carbon Observatory-3 (OCO-3), and Jason Continuity of Service (Jason-CS) mission (planned in coordination with ESA’s Sentinel 6).

In addition to the missions and instruments detailed above, the responsibility of several climate sensors has been transferred from the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) to NASA. These climate sensors include the Radiation Budget Instrument (RBI), Total and Spectral Solar Irradiance Sensor (TSIS), and Ozone Mapping and Profiler Suite – Limb (OMPS-L).

The Earth science flight program portfolio is expected to grow further, as the selection process is underway for the

next EVI and an Announcement of Opportunity is currently out for the next EVM. Additionally, the Earth science flight program is funding pre-formulation studies for several other missions that may become development projects. Figure 4 depicts the planned NASA Earth science missions.

4. AIRBORNE SCIENCE PROGRAM

The Airborne Science Program (ASP) within the Earth Science Division is responsible for providing aircraft systems and infrastructure that furthers Earth science and advances the use of Earth science satellite data. The program provides airborne platforms to enable essential calibration measurements for the Earth observing satellites, and the validation of data retrieval algorithms. It provides sub-orbital flight opportunities to test and refine new instrument technologies, algorithms, and to reduce risks prior to committing sensors for launch into space. The ASP obtains high-resolution temporal and spatial measurements of complex earth system processes, which can be coupled to global satellite observations for a better understanding of the complete Earth system. It has also been utilized as a gap filler to provide coverage of the Earth between satellite missions. One such gap-filling mission is Operation IceBridge. Operation IceBridge makes airborne altimetry, radar, and other geophysical measurements to monitor and characterize the Earth’s cryosphere to extend the record started by ICESat, and will be flown until ICESat-2 is launched.

Figure 4. Future Earth Science Missions

ASP maintains and operates a suite of airborne platforms and sensors on which investigators can rely from year to year. Airborne platforms are located throughout the country and include NASA owned and operated aircraft as well as a variety of other governmental and commercial aircraft providers. NASA platforms include Beechcraft B-200's, a Boeing DC-8, several Gulfstream GIII's, a Northrop Grumman Global Hawk, two Lockheed Martin ER-2's, a Lockheed Martin P-3, and two Lockheed Martin C-130's. In addition, the ASP also provides a range of support functions including instrument integration and design, online tools for mission planning and real time tracking of aircraft, as well as worldwide logistics support. The program continually seeks new or evolving technologies to enhance the efficient and effective utilization of Earth Science Division resources to perform the airborne mission. Figure 5 shows the ASP campaigns flown from 2005 to 2015.

5. EARTH SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY

ESTO funds, develops and demonstrates cutting-edge technologies that can be reliably applied to the diverse needs of future NASA Earth science measurements and missions. From next generation sensors and instruments to communication systems and computer modeling, ESTO technologies enable new or improved observations and insights of our home planet.

ESTO funds new competitively selected technologies, driven by the needs of the science community, through four main programs. These programs include Advanced Technology Initiatives (ATI), Observations Technologies consisting of the Instrument Incubator Program (IIP) and

Advanced Component Technologies (ACT), Advanced Information Systems Technology (AIST) and In-Space Validation of Earth Science Technologies (InVEST).

IIP funds remote sensing instrument development from concept through breadboard and demonstration while ACT manages projects focused on component and subsystem development to be used as part of advanced instruments and systems. ATI leverages investments through partnerships with other Earth Science Division programs to further develop science-ready instruments deemed highly useful by the community. AIST projects cover integral aspects of data acquisition and use including data handling, processing, access, sensor networks, high-performance computing and modeling applications. ESTO's newest program, InVEST, provides an avenue for emerging technologies to demonstrate and validate their performance through early space flight opportunities to increase readiness and lower the risk for future Earth observing missions.

ESTO investments are often matured to the point that they can be infused into upcoming Earth science missions. For example, the Prototype HypsIRI Thermal Infrared Radiometer (PHYTIR), funded through IIP and completed in 2014 was selected as a NASA EVI, ECOSTRESS, to measure and monitor plant-water dynamics and evapotranspiration. The upcoming SWOT mission will utilize a lightweight deployable mast that was developed under ACT. AIST-selected soil moisture sensor web work is being used to validate the measurements taken by the Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP) mission.

ESTO's current and recently completed projects continue to work on a path toward infusion, including the InVEST

Figure 5. Airborne Science Campaigns 2005-2015

selections.

The InVEST CubeSats show promise of supporting NASA’s Earth science measurement objectives. The Compact Infrared Radiometer in Space (CIRiS) was selected by ESTO to validate an uncooled imaging infrared radiometer for high radiometric performance in low Earth orbit. CIRiS’s measurements are directly related to the radiometric measurements of Landsat missions. As such, the measurements collected by flying five CIRiS satellites are comparable to the measurements of Landsat 8 and could be used as a calibrator for Landsat 9.

Radar in a CubeSat (RainCube) will be the first orbiting active radar instrument on a CubeSat platform. It was funded to validate a precipitation Ka-Band radar payload using new deployable antenna and processing technologies.

Another newly selected InVEST award, Cubesat Infrared Atmospheric Sounder (CIRAS), funded to demonstrate the ability to measure upwelling infrared radiation, has the potential to be used as a gap-filler for the Cross-track Infrared Sounder (CrIS) instrument that produces high-resolution, three-dimensional temperature, pressure, and moisture profiles.

The Linear Mode Photon Counting (LMPC) CubeSat will provide a new capability, a space qualified photon level detector greater than 1 micron. LMPC could be infused into lidar mapping, trace gas detection and large array passive sensing missions from 0.7 to 4.0 microns and would be useful for any of the Active Sensing of CO2 Emissions over Nights, Days, and Seasons (ASCENDS) concepts currently under study in the NASA Earth science flight program.

These and other ESTO investments are continuing on the path to infusion, to be used as reliable Earth observing instruments, systems, and validation techniques for NASA’s Earth Science Division.

6. DATA COLLECTION AND ARCHIVING

NASA has been collecting data from Earth observations for over 50 years using spaceborne, airborne and ground-based instruments. Among the early spaceborne missions were the Nimbus series of satellites and the Landsat series, the latter of which continues to the present day. The Earth Observing System (EOS) Program was initiated by NASA in 1990, resulting in a series of satellite launches, starting with the TRMM in 1997. This was followed by Landsat-7 and Terra (1999), Aqua (2002), ICESat (2003), Aura (2004), and other smaller satellites. Most of the EOS satellites continue to operate and provide a wealth of measurements of various parameters that characterize the Earth. Following the EOS Program, there are the Suomi-NPP, the Decadal Survey satellite missions and satellite missions that are part of ESSP. Also, there are several aircraft campaigns under EVS. In addition, there are many field campaigns and validation projects supported by NASA that result in hundreds of data

products. The data from all these sources constitute a valuable national resource, which is extremely useful for scientific research and applications on a global scale. In recognition of this, at the inception of the EOS Program, NASA established the ESDIS Project to develop and operate the EOSDIS. The ESDIS Project is responsible for archiving and distribution of most of NASA’s Earth science data.

Today, EOSDIS, consists of 12 Earth science-discipline based Distributed Active Archive Centers (DAACs) and 12 Science Investigator-led Processing Systems (SIPS). The data held by EOSDIS are available to all users, consistent with NASA’s free and open data policy, which has been in effect since 1990. The EOSDIS archives consist of raw instrument data counts (level 0 data), as well as higher level standard products (e.g., geophysical parameters, products mapped to standard spatio-temporal grids, results of Earth system models using multi-instrument observations, and long time series of Earth System Data Records resulting from multiple satellite observations of a given type of phenomenon). The EOSDIS has been distributing data to a broad, diverse and global user community since 1994. During 2014, the distribution from EOSDIS exceeded one billion files (see figure 6). Table 2 summarizes the scope and capability of this massive data resource.

Figure 6. EOSDIS Science Data Products Distribution FY2000 - FY2014

Table 2. EOSDIS Metrics

EOSDIS Metrics (Oct 1, 2013 to Sept 30, 2014)	
Unique Data Products (Collections)	8,292
Distinct Users of EOSDIS Data and Services	2.0 M
Web Site Visits of 1 Minute or more	2.3 M
Average Daily Archive Growth	6.4 TB/day
Total Archive Volume (as of Sept. 30, 2014)	9.1 PB
End User Distribution Products per year	1,028 M
End User Average Daily Distribution Volume	27.9 TB/day

7. SUMMARY

NASA's Earth science flight program is a diverse and vigorous enterprise. While the operational fleet faces challenges, such as aging assets and collision avoidance, the missions continue to produce world-class science data. The flight program is evolving with a robust set of systematic and pathfinder missions in development and formulation. In addition to the space-based missions, NASA also has a dynamic set of airborne activities, that deliver important science and complement space missions. NASA Earth science also has a successful technology development program that creates opportunities for future spaceborne and airborne science investigations. All of the data collected by NASA's Earth science projects are freely available to the public through the capabilities of EOSDIS. The NASA Earth science flight program is meeting the challenges of today and is well positioned to continue to prosper in the future.

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ACRONYMS

ACRIMSAT	Active Cavity Radiometer Irradiance Monitor Satellite	GEDI	Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation
ACT	Advanced Component Technologies	GFZ	German Research Centre for Geosciences
AIST	Advanced Information Systems Technology	GPM	Global Precipitation Measurement
ASCENDS	Active Sending CO ₂ Emissions over Nights, Days, and Seasons	GPS	Global Positioning System
ASP	Airborne Science Program	GRACE	Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment
ATI	Advanced Technology Initiatives	GRACE-FO	Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment - Follow On
CALIPSO	Cloud-Aerosol Lidar and Infrared Pathfinder Satellite Observations	HypIRI	Hyperspectral Infrared Imager
CATS	Cloud-Aerosol Transport System	ICESat-2	Ice, Cloud, and land Elevation Satellite-2
CIRAS	Cubesat Infrared Atmospheric Sounder	IIP	Instrument Incubator Program
CIRiS	Compact Infrared Radiometer in Space	InVEST	In-Space Validation of Earth Science Technologies
CLARREO	Climate Absolute Radiance and Refractivity Observatory	ISRO	Indian Space Research Organisation
CNES	Centre National d'Etudes Spatiales	ISS	International Space Station
CrIS	Cross-track Infrared Sounder	JPSS	Joint Polar Satellite System
CYGNSS	Cyclone Global Navigation Satellite System	L9	Landsat 9
DAAC	Distributed Active Archive Center	LMPC	Linear Mode Photon Counting
DSCOVR	Deep Space Climate Observatory	NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
ECOSTRESS	ECOsystem Spaceborne Thermal Radiometer Experiment on Space Station	NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
EO-1	Earth Observing-1	NISAR	NASA-ISRO Synthetic Aperture Radar
EOS	Earth Observing System	OCO-2	Orbiting Carbon Observatory-2
EOSDIS	Earth Observing System Data and Information System	OCO-3	Orbiting Carbon Observatory-3
ESDIS	Earth Science Data and Information System	OMPS-L	Ozone Mapping and Profiler Suite - Limb
ESM	Earth Systematic Mission	OSTM	Ocean Surface Topography Mission
ESSP	Earth System Science Pathfinder	PACE	Pre-Aerosol, Clouds, and ocean Ecosystem
ESA	European Space Agency	PHyTIR	Prototype HypIRI Thermal Infrared Radiometer
ESTO	Earth Science Technology Office	PI	Principal Investigator
EVI	Earth Venture Instrument	RBI	Radiation Budget Instrument
EVM	Earth Venture Mission	SAGE III	Stratospheric Aerosol and Gas Experiment III
EVS	Earth Venture Suborbital	SIPS	Science Investigator-led Processing Systems
		SMAP	Soil Moisture Active Passive
		SORCE	Solar Radiation and Climate Experiment

Suomi NPP	Suomi National Polar-orbiting Partnership
SWOT	Surface Water and Ocean Topography
TEMPO	Tropospheric Emissions: Monitoring of Pollution
TRMM	Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission
TSIS	Total and Spectral Solar Irradiance Sensor
USGS	United States Geological Survey

BIOGRAPHY

Eric E. Ianson received a B.S. degree in Mechanical Engineering from the University of Rochester and an M.S. degree in Aerospace Engineering from the University of Southern California. He is also a graduate of the “Leadership for a Democratic Society” program at the Federal Executive Institute. Mr.

Ianson is currently the Associate Director of Flight Programs in the Earth Science Division of the Science Mission Directorate at NASA Headquarters. In this role, he oversees all NASA Earth science satellite and airborne programs and projects, as well as the data systems that house and distribute the data from these programs and projects. He previously served as the Deputy Associate Director for the Earth Science Projects Division at Goddard Space Flight Center (GSFC), a Program Executive at NASA Headquarters, and a Mission Manager at GSFC. Prior to joining NASA, Mr. Ianson worked for the Department of Defense for 14 years, involved in program and project oversight for the U.S. Navy on missiles, combat systems and associated equipment.

George J. Komar has over 38 years of experience in engineering, program, project and operational management. Presently he serves as the Associate Director in the Earth Science Division and Program Manager for the Earth Science Technology Office (ESTO) for NASA. In this capacity he is

responsible for developing, integrating and managing all the advanced technology developments that will enable future Earth science capabilities. He has previously served as the Deputy Associate Administrator for Technology for the NASA Science Mission Directorate (SMD), Program Manager for Landsat 7 and TOPEX/Poseidon and managed the integration of the NASA Space Station Ground System Program for the ISS. Prior to coming to NASA, Mr. Komar spent 21 years in the US Air Force. He flew numerous flights and coordinated all Air Force headquarters activities for strategic airlift weapons system acquisition programs. He has received numerous awards and honors, including the NASA Medal for Exceptional Achievement and NASA Exceptional Leadership Medal.

Kevin Murphy received a B.S. in geography and remote sensing from Clark University in 1997 and an M.S. in geographical sciences, with a concentration in land cover remote sensing, from the University of Maryland. He is currently the

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Cheryl Yuhás received a B.S. degree in Physics/Astronomy from the University of Michigan. She is currently the Operating Missions Program Executive for the Earth Science Division in NASA’s Science Mission Directorate at NASA Headquarters. In this position she oversees the operation of the 19

missions currently on-orbit, monitoring their performance against the missions’ science objectives and managing the biennial mission extension process known as the Senior Review. She joined NASA in 1991 and worked as Program Executive for several Earth Science missions during their development phase, then managed the Suborbital Science Program for both the Space and Earth Science Divisions, before returning to the orbiting missions in 2006. Ms. Yuhás is the recipient of numerous awards and honors, including the NASA Exceptional Achievement Medal.

